

Substitution-boxes based on Binary Tree built by Variants of Depth First Search

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Abstract—In today's age maximum communication takes place through internet and online channels. Therefore, securing of data has become even more vital and to fulfil this purpose data is encrypted in an unreadable form known as cryptography. S-box is established to obtain this purpose because it provides data obscurity, dependability and power to withstand against attacks from illegal resources. This paper shows the construction of resilient and robust S-boxes based on binary tree built by variants of Depth First Search. We tested our S-boxes using different analyses such as algebraic, statistical and also for image encryption.

Index Terms—Tree traversal, binary tree, Depth First Search, variants of DFS, adjacency matrix, Substitution box

I. INTRODUCTION

In this era, most of the communication and transfer of data takes place through the internet. For secure and reliable transmission of data and to protect it from manipulation and modification, cryptography plays an important role. Cryptography aims to hide secret information from illegal access by using encryption techniques that helps in secure transmission of data [1]. The word cryptography is derived from the Greek language, *kryptos* means to hide and *graphein* means to write. The plaintext (message) is sent from the sender to the receiver in the ciphertext (encrypted message) so that only the receiver can interpret and understand it [3]. The procedure of encrypting the unencrypted text into cipher text is called encryption and the conversion of encrypted text into unencrypted text is called decryption. In order to provide secrecy to the plaintext different cryptographic techniques are used which includes symmetric key cryptography and asymmetric key cryptography. In symmetric key cryptography same key is shared between sender and receiver. Block ciphers and stream ciphers are two main branches of symmetric key cryptography. Symmetric key encryption algorithms are fastest among all encryption algorithms because they encrypt large amount of data. Block ciphers processes plaintext of fixed length whereas stream ciphers processes plaintext of arbitrary length. If the block length of the block cipher exceeds the length of the plaintext many modes of operations are used. Some of them use stream ciphers. Thus block ciphers are also known as building block for stream ciphers [2]. In the field of cryptography, Shannon presented the idea of block ciphers in 1949. Block ciphers are major component of cryptography that are based on Shannon's principle of confusion and diffusion. In 1997 National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) felt the need for new encryption because of weak performances by Data Encryption Standard (DES) to make data more secure and reliable among many algorithms presented in 1997 finally Rijndael was proclaimed to be the safest and final encryption standard known as Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) in November 2001. The block size of AES is 128 bits and the variable key size is 128, 192 and 256 bits, depending on the size of the key length the processing rounds are 10, 12 and 14. The strength of the S-box depends on its nonlinearity and it becomes more efficient and robust against different cryptanalysis attacks [4]. Symmetric block ciphers are mostly used because they are easy to use and provide strong cryptographic strength. Substitution box (S-box) creates uncertainty and non-linearity and it is an important component of block ciphers [5]. S-Box is the nonlinear component

of symmetric key cryptography and it plays a very vital role during enciphering of the digital data [6]. We come across various Substitution boxes (S-boxes) designed by different cryptographers that are found in literature. In [7] the authors used permutation of symmetric group of size 8 and bitwise XOR operation and designed various S-boxes that exhibit good resistance against different attacks made by cryptanalysis. In [8] the authors rather than using the whole Galois field used the multiplicative subgroup of Galois field to construct an S-box. Motivated by the research studies [9,10] we will construct S-boxes using binary tree built by variants of Depth First Search (DFS).

A. Paper contributions and organizations

This methodology shows a new technique for designing resilient S-boxes using binary tree built by variants of DFS. Variants of DFS that are used for tree traversal are preorder, inorder and postorder traversal that result in the formation of binary tree. After applying adjacency matrix on the binary tree we obtained 8×8 matrix. The result showed no uniqueness when we applied action of matrix on $GF(2^8)$ so inorder to obtain uniqueness we then applied transformation ω on $GF(2^8)$. The arrangement of the paper is given as follows: Section 2 describes concept about variants of DFS for tree traversal that will result in the formation of binary tree and adjacency matrix. Section 3 describes the new technique for designing resilient and robust S-boxes. Section 4 explains algebraic analyses to check the performance of proposed S-boxes. Section 5 describes the image encryption scheme for the proposed S-boxes and in last Section 6 describes the conclusion of this research paper.

II. MATHEMATICAL PRELIMINARIES

This section explains the concept about binary tree built by variants of DFS for tree traversal and adjacency matrix used in the construction of 8×8 S-boxes.

A. Variants of Depth First Search for tree traversal

A tree is a nonlinear data structure used for graphical representation of data which is hierarchical in nature. A tree contains arcs and nodes and to reach each node a unique sequence of arc is followed that is called path. Root node contains no parent but it consists of child node or leaf node that has no children [11]. In tree traversal all the nodes of a tree are visited only once. This is also called searching a tree. There are many possibilities for traversing a tree but to classify the possibilities for traversing a tree, variants of DFS are used. Depth First Search first visits the root node and then the left or right subtrees in a tree as deep as possible to the left or right and when all nodes are visited it backtracks. This process continues until all nodes are visited. Variants of DFS includes preorder traversal, inorder traversal and postorder traversal. In preorder traversal, the current root node is processed then the left subtree is processed as deep as possible until a leaf node is found in that case perform backtracking and then right subtree is processed. In inorder traversal, the root node is processed between the subtrees which means the left subtree is processed, then the current node is processed and afterward right subtree is processed. In postorder traversal, the root node is visited after both subtrees i.e. left subtree is processed, then the right subtree is visited and then current root node is processed. Tree traversal is an important characteristics of binary tree. A node of a tree has no child, one child or two children is called a binary tree [12]. When we traverse a tree using variants of DFS i.e. postorder traversal and inorder traversal or preorder traversal and inorder traversal a binary tree is constructed [13,14].

B. Adjacency matrix

Adjacency matrix exhibits a finite graph $G = (V, E)$ where V denotes vertices known as nodes and must be non-empty and E denotes edges known as arcs where each edge form pairs of vertices from nodes. It is a square matrix and for undirected graph it is always symmetric. If there is an edge from v_i to v_j and $(v_i, v_j) = (v_j, v_i)$ the value is one and zero otherwise [11].

III. PROCEDURE FOR CONSTRUCTING RESILIENT AND ROBUST PROPOSED 8×8 S-BOXES

We used binary field Z_2 for $GF(2^8)$ with 256 elements for constructing resilient S-boxes. There are thirty irreducible polynomial for binary field Z_2 and out of those thirty, sixteen are primitive irreducible polynomial [15]. $\gamma(x) = x^8 + x^4 + x^3 + x + 1$ is used as primitive irreducible polynomial in AES. In [16] the authors used $\gamma(x) = x^8 + x^6 + x^5 + x^4 + 1$ as primitive irreducible polynomial. We can construct different S-boxes if we change the primitive irreducible polynomial. To construct our S-boxes we used $\gamma(x) = x^8 + x^4 + x^3 + x^2 + 1$ as primitive irreducible polynomial. Figure 1 describes the flowchart representation of algorithm.

Figure 1. Flowchart representation of algorithm

This binary tree will be constructed using postorder and inorder variants of Depth First Search.

Postorder: 4,5,2,8,6,7,3,1 [Left subtree, Right subtree, Root]

Inorder: 4,2,5,1,6,8,3,7 [Left subtree, Root, Right subtree]

Step 1

Start finding the root in postorder from right to left. Mark or circle the considered root node in the inorder traversal and write the elements of the left subtree and right subtree.

Step 2

To find the nearest root node in the left subtree of node 1, we will again search in the postorder from right to left, the nearest traversal will be the left subtree root node i.e. node 2. Circle the root node in the inorder traversal and write the elements of the left subtree and right subtree. Node 4 is the left subtree root node of node 2.

Postorder: 4,5,2,8,6,7,3,1

Inorder: 4 2 5,1,6,8,3,7

Step 3

Circle node 4 in the inorder traversal. Node 4 is a leaf node so we will backtrack from node 4 to node 2 to find its nearest right subtree root node as deep as possible until we find a leaf node.

Postorder: 4,5,2,8,6,7,3,1

Inorder: 4 2,5,1,6,8,3,7

Step 4

Node 5 is the right subtree root node of node 2. Circle 5 in the inorder traversal. Node 5 is a leaf node so backtrack from node 5 to node 2 and then backtrack to the root node 1.

Postorder: 4,5,2,8,6,7,3,1

Inorder: 4, 2, 5, 1,6,8,3,7

Step 5

Now we will traverse the nearest root node of the right subtree of root node 1. We will again search from right to left in postorder traversal. Circle 3 in the inorder traversal and write the elements of the left subtree and right subtree.

Postorder: 4,5,2,8,6,7,3,1

Inorder: 4,2,5, 1,6,8, 3, 7

Step 6

Now we will traverse in the postorder traversal to find the nearest root node of the left subtree of node 3. The nearest root node is node 6. Circle 6 in the inorder traversal, and we will traverse in the postorder traversal to find its left and right subtree. It has no left subtree and node 8 is the root node of its right subtree.

Postorder: 4,5,2,8,6,7,3,1

Inorder: 4,2,5, 1, 6, 8, 3,7

Step 7

Circle 8 in the inorder traversal. Node 8 is a leaf node, it has no left and right subtree. We will backtrack from 8 to node 6 and then backtrack from node 6 to node 3 and will find the nearest root node of the right subtree of node 3.

Postorder: 4,5,2,8,6,7,3,1
 Inorder: 4,2,5, 1,6, 8, 3,7

Step 8

Circle 3 in the inorder traversal. Node 7 is the root node of its right subtree.

Postorder: 4,5,2,8,6,7,3,1
 Inorder: 4,2,5, 1,6,8, 3, 7

Right subtree

Step 9

Circle 7 in the inorder traversal. Node 7 is a leaf node. Backtrack from node 7 to node 3 and from node 3 to node 1. The tree constructed using this method is called binary tree shown in figure 2

Postorder: 4,5,2,8,6,7,3,1
 Inorder: 4,2,5, 1,6,8, 3 (7)

Figure 2. Binary tree

Adjacency matrix ‘E’ constructed using binary tree given in Figure 2, is given below where the vertices are labeled as 1,2,3,4,5,6,7 and 8.

$$E = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

After applying the obtained adjacency matrix E on $GF(2^8)$ the results revealed no uniqueness. As elements of S-box must indicate uniqueness and for this reason, we develop the transformation ω on $GF(2^8)$ as shown in (1).

$$\omega(c_n) = Ec_n + c_{n+i(mod\ 256)} \quad (1)$$

In the Equation (1), c_n represent the elements of Galois field $GF(2^8)$ where $n = 0, 1, 2, 3 \dots, 255$. We checked all the values from 0 to 255 in i using (1) and found that for $i = 2, 8, 16$ and 32 different S-box is constructed for each value of i . We choose $i = 16$ for the construction process of the proposed S-box I as shown in Table 1. Proposed S-box I for $i = 16$ is shown in Table 2.

TABLE 1. CONSTRUCTION OF THE PROPOSED S-BOX I FOR $i = 16$

$GF(2^8)$	$\omega(c_n) = Ec_n + c_{n+i(mod\ 256)}$	Proposed robust S-box
0	$\omega(c_0) = Ec_0 + c_{0+16(mod\ 256)}$	0
1	$\omega(c_1) = Ec_1 + c_{1+16(mod\ 256)}$	186
2	$\omega(c_2) = Ec_2 + c_{2+16(mod\ 256)}$	128
.	.	
.	.	
254	$\omega(c_{254}) = Ec_{254} + c_{254+16(mod\ 256)}$	70
255	$\omega(c_{255}) = Ec_{255} + c_{255+16(mod\ 256)}$	130

TABLE 2. PROPOSED S-BOX I FOR $i = 16$

0	186	128	160	196	202	254	119	221	170	114	76	50	82	233	217
68	188	49	2	201	227	109	180	11	162	29	124	255	232	226	63
52	198	182	197	89	163	118	10	190	59	242	238	90	133	41	214
64	137	139	31	140	129	48	147	171	169	138	108	193	55	248	78
146	213	65	19	237	44	207	12	69	136	26	104	74	38	72	94
215	113	125	98	107	235	206	183	153	120	158	18	100	174	159	194
20	241	117	127	204	161	199	220	243	33	231	211	245	73	155	79
17	251	141	47	102	216	61	152	219	252	91	185	131	85	122	1
28	5	123	149	184	165	25	115	13	8	229	191	58	210	249	246
111	195	208	51	97	56	22	30	80	225	81	96	14	203	166	95
71	244	42	144	87	23	6	205	93	157	62	192	179	32	40	121
15	223	105	39	234	3	250	106	172	148	176	27	212	126	230	177
134	240	253	66	84	228	189	9	178	116	143	181	45	83	24	92
218	209	236	239	88	224	173	150	132	187	77	36	222	75	142	167
54	4	99	151	86	57	21	34	43	103	35	37	110	112	164	46
200	67	247	168	175	135	156	60	16	145	53	101	154	7	70	130

Now we will construct the binary tree using preorder and inorder variants of DFS

Preorder 1,2,3,5,6,4,7,8 [Root, Left subtree, Right subtree]

Inorder: 5,3,6,2,4,1,7,8 [Left subtree, Root, Right subtree]

Step1

Start finding the root node in pre order from left to right. Mark or circle the considered root node in the inorder traversal

Preorder: 1,2,3,5,6,4,7,8

Step 2 To find root in the left subtree of node1, we will again search in the preorder from left to right, the nearest traversal will be the left subtree root node. Circle 2 in the inorder traversal and write its left subtree and right subtree.

Step 3

To find root node in the left subtree of node 2, we will again search in the preorder from left to right, the nearest traversal will be the left subtree root node. Circle 3 in the inorder traversal and write its left subtree and right subtree.

Step 4

To find root node in the left subtree of node 3, we will again search in the preorder from left to right, the nearest traversal will be the left subtree root node. Circle 5 in the inorder traversal and write its left subtree and right subtree. Node 5 is a leaf node. Backtrack from node 5 to node 3.

Step 5

To find the root node in the right subtree of node 3, again traverse in the preorder from left to right. Node 6 is the root node of the right subtree. Circle 6 in the inorder traversal. Node 6 is a leaf node because it has no left and right subtree. Backtrack from node 6 to node 3.

Preorder: 1,2,3,5,6,4,7,8
 Inorder: 5,3,6,2,4,1,7,8

Step 6

To find root in the right subtree of root node 2, we will backtrack from node 3 to node 2 and will again search in the preorder from left to right, the nearest traversal will be the right subtree root node. Circle 4 in the inorder traversal and write its left subtree and right subtree. Node 4 is a leaf node. Backtrack from node 4 to node 2.

Preorder: 1,2,3,5,6,4,7,8
 Inorder: 5,3,6,2,4,1,7,8

Step 7

To find root node of the right subtree of node 1, backtrack from node 2 to node 1 and traverse in the preorder traversal. The nearest traversal will be the right subtree root node. Circle 7 in the inorder traversal and write the elements of its left subtree and right subtree.

Step 8

Node 8 is the root node of the right subtree of node 7. Circle 8 in the inorder traversal. Node 8 is a leaf node. Back track from node 8 to node 7 and from node 7 to node 1. Binary tree constructed using preorder and inorder variants of DFS is given in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Binary tree

Adjacency matrix 'G' constructed using binary tree given in Figure 3, is given below where the vertices are labeled as 1,2,3,4,5,6,7 and 8.

$$G = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Replacing E by G in (1) and by applying the obtained adjacency matrix G on elements of $GF(2^8)$ the results revealed no uniqueness. As elements of S-box must indicate uniqueness so for this reason, we again used the transformation ω on elements of $GF(2^8)$ in (1). Again we checked all the numbers from 0 to 255 in i using (1) and found that different S-boxes can be constructed for $i = 2, 64, 128$ and 192. We choose $i = 2$ for the construction of S-box II. Proposed S-box II for $i = 2$ is shown in Table 3.

TABLE 3. PROPOSED S-BOX II FOR $i = 2$

0	213	150	22	64	251	34	6	221	136	167	166	171	252	46	40
224	97	128	19	57	87	139	47	75	14	114	104	112	179	138	185
96	77	74	82	192	35	131	55	51	236	237	202	144	99	102	129
72	217	225	132	122	78	157	43	207	119	195	218	61	147	244	54
89	161	168	105	201	235	66	123	90	73	101	176	255	174	181	229
67	15	118	220	240	28	109	183	145	172	41	79	116	13	226	194
177	70	243	59	246	24	153	162	106	156	20	198	115	189	215	188
231	238	126	154	158	124	210	45	117	197	3	175	125	2	165	84
18	29	58	83	211	242	212	7	98	49	184	228	127	182	234	135
249	92	120	11	230	130	33	190	25	9	113	68	250	60	241	52
134	5	180	206	200	223	10	199	178	8	63	159	16	148	214	155
227	107	253	149	163	204	247	39	232	100	143	191	133	245	53	27
1	248	93	103	94	233	80	187	152	48	71	4	12	254	111	209
62	37	85	193	81	36	38	50	42	151	216	140	208	239	44	196
86	23	31	141	88	56	160	65	110	32	108	91	222	203	76	26
137	17	21	205	186	146	173	30	169	219	164	121	170	69	142	95

IV. ALGEBRAIC ANALYSES OF THE PROPOSED S-BOXES

The algebraic analyses include nonlinearity [17], strict avalanche criterion (SAC) [9], bit independence criterion (BIC) [10], linear probability (LP) and differential probability (DP) [18] By using S-box tool [19], we checked the algebraic analyses of our proposed S-boxes. The results are shown in Tables 4-5 . Table 5 gives the comparison of our proposed S-boxes with existing S-boxes.

A. Nonlinearity

The set of all affine functions and the distance between the function is called Boolean function's nonlinearity. In Boolean function's truth table, the number of bits must be amended to approach the closest affine function. In AES S-box over $GF(2^8)$ the maximum nonlinearity is 120. The nonlinearity of an S-box over the $GF(2^n)$ is defined as $N(f) = 2^{n-1} - 2^{\frac{n}{2}-1}$ [20]. The average nonlinearity for our proposed S-box I and S-box II is 112 as shown in Table 4.

B. Strict Avalanche Criterion(SAC)

In this analysis, changing a single input bit consequently changes each output bit with a probability of 50% [21]. The SAC values of our proposed S-boxes is given in Table 4 and their values are near to 0.5 that satisfies SAC criterion.

C. Bit Independence Criterion(BIC)

Webster and Tavares presented the Bit Independence Criterion (BIC) [22] and this is used to evaluate the independence between the avalanche variables. The individual input bits are complemented and the output vectors are examined for independence [9]. The BIC of our proposed S-boxes is shown in Table 4 and Table 5 shows the comparison of our proposed S-boxes with the existing S-boxes. The comparison with already existing S-boxes shows that our proposed S-boxes depict good cryptographic strength.

D. Differential Probability (DP)

Differential uniformity measures Differential Probability of an S-box. It is an important trait that highlights the oneness of the S-box. The equation for calculating Differential Probability of an S-box is given in (2).

$$DP_{(\Delta r \rightarrow \Delta y)}^S = \left[\frac{\#\{x \in X | S(x) \pm S(x \pm \Delta r) = \Delta y\}}{2^n} \right] \quad (2)$$

DP guarantees uniform mapping. In (2), X denotes the set of all likely inputs, 2^n denotes the number of its elements, Δr denotes input differential and Δy denotes output differential. There is a unique mapping from input differential Δr to the output differential Δy . The DP values of our proposed S-boxes is shown in Table 4 and its comparison with other S-boxes is shown in Table 5. The comparison shows that the DP value of our proposed S-boxes is 0.0156 that is similar to the DP value of AES, APA and Gray that represent good cryptographic strength [32].

E. Linear Probability (LP)

The Linear Probability method analyzes the maximum imbalance value of the output in an event. The equation for calculating Linear Probability is given in (3).

$$LP = \max_{\tau_x, \tau_y} \left| \frac{\#\{x | x \cdot \tau_x = S(x) \cdot \tau_y\}}{2^n} - \frac{1}{2} \right| \quad (3)$$

In eq (3), x and y denotes the input bits and the output bits, 2^n denotes the number of elements. The two masks τ_x and τ_y are applied to the parity of the input and output bits [23]. Table 4 shows LP value of our proposed S-boxes and Table 5 shows comparison with the other S-boxes.

F. Discussions

The comparison of the proposed S-boxes with the distinguished S-boxes based on algebraic analyses is described

in Table 5 and graphical representation of Table 5 is shown in Figure 4. Our proposed S-boxes show maximum nonlinearity i.e. 112. Maximum BIC i.e. 112. Table 5 describes the SAC value of proposed S-boxes. The DP and LP values of our proposed S-boxes are similar to AES, APA and Gray that is adequate for cryptographically strong S-box. Our S-box shows good cryptographic strength and possess good algebraic analyses as compared to the [24]- [28], [17], [29], [18], [30], [20] and [31]- [32].

Proposed S-box I				
Analysis	Maximum	Minimum	Average	Square Deviation
Nonlinearity	112	112	112	0
SAC	0.5468	0.4531	0.4990	0.0302
BIC	-	112	112	0
BIC-SAC	-	0.4804	0.4992	0.0100
DP	0.0156	-	-	-
LP	0.0625	-	-	-
Proposed S-box II				
Nonlinearity	112	112	112	0
SAC	0.5625	0.4375	0.5000	0.0304
BIC	-	112	112	0
BIC-SAC	-	0.4843	0.5014	0.0089
DP	0.0156	-	-	-
LP	0.0625	-	-	-

TABLE 4. THE ALGEBRAIC ANALYSES OF OUR PROPOSED S-BOXES

TABLE5. THE COMPARISON OF ALGEBRAIC ANALYSES OF OUR PROPOSED S-BOXES WITH OTHER S-BOXES

S-box	Nonlinearity	SAC	BIC	LP	DP
Proposed S-box I	112	0.4990	112	0.0625	0.0156
Proposed S-box II	112	0.5000	112	0.0625	0.0156
AES [24]	112	0.5058	112	0.0625	0.0156
APA [25]	112	0.4987	112	0.0625	0.0156
Gray [26]	112	0.505	111.46	0.0664	0.0156
Skipjack [27]	105.75	0.503	104.14	0.109	0.0468
Xyi [28]	105	0.502	103.78	0.156	0.0468
Wajeaha et al. [17]	105.83	0.4975	103.07	0.129	0.0390
I. Shahzad et al. [29]	110.50	0.5031	109.21	0.0860	0.0234
S. Farwa et al. [18]	103.5	0.5065	103.3	0.1328	0.0468
M. F. Khan et al. [30]	111	0.5036	110.0	0.0781	0.0234
U. Hayat et al. [20]	100	0.5007	104.1	0.0390	0.1250
A. Zahid et al. [31]	107.0	0.497	103.5	0.1560	0.0390
N. Siddiqui et al. [32]	104	0.500	103.14	0.125	0.039

Figure 4. Graphical representation of Table 5

V. IMAGE ENCRYPTION APPLICATION FOR PROPOSED S-BOXES

The statistical analyses on image encryption application is based on majority logic criterion (MLC) [21]. Its purpose is to deform the image and this deformation represents the authenticity of the application. This analyses include entropy, contrast, correlation, energy and homogeneity test [29] as follows:

A. Entropy

The randomness in picture is measured in entropy. The degree of entropy is linked with the object's organizations in image. High level randomness creates ambiguity in the image which is achieved by nonlinear components substitution in the system [9]. Mathematical equation for entropy is given in (4).

$$H = - \sum_{l=0}^n p(x_l) \log_b p(x_l) \quad (4)$$

In (4), x_l denotes the histogram calculations.

B. Contrast

The potential to recognize objects in an image is encompassed in contrast analysis. Contrast parameters evaluate the efficiency of an S-box. The encrypted image with higher level of randomness represent data reliability. The image which is constant has zero value [23]. The mathematical equation for contrast is given in (5).

$$C = \sum_{q,w} (q - w)^2 p(q, w) \quad (5)$$

C. Correlation

Correlation of a pixel to its neighbor is assessed in three different formats that include vertical, horizontal and diagonal. The mathematical expression for correlation is given in (6).

$$K = \sum_{q,w} \frac{(q - \mu_q)(w - \mu_w)p(q, w)}{\sigma_q \sigma_w} \quad (6)$$

In (6), $p(q, w)$ represents the value of pixel, q represents the row position and w represents the column position in digital images. μ and σ are the parameters that denotes variance and standard deviation [5]. The image i.e. constant has zero value and for image i.e. positive and negative has 1 or -1 values. If there is weak correlation it means that correlation near to zero [10].

D. Energy

The energy level of image which is encrypted by using Gray-Level Co-occurrence Matrix (GLCM) is measured in this analysis. Energy analysis measures the sum of squared parts of GLCM. The mathematical equation for energy analysis is given in (7).

$$E = \sum_{q,w} p^2(q, w) \quad (7)$$

In (7), q and w shows the image pixels and $p(q, w)$ shows the number of GLCM. The value of energy is 1 for constant image [21].

E. Homogeneity

The compactness of distributed elements of GLCM to GLCM diagonal is measured in this analysis. During encryption the small value of homogeneity shows the robustness of encryption algorithm [33]. The equation for homogeneity is given in (8).

$$H = \sum_q \sum_w \frac{p(q, w)}{1 + |q - w|} \quad (8)$$

For MLC test we used jpeg images of Pepper and Baboon. We ran this test on MATLAB tool. We performed one round encryption on Pepper and Baboon's plain images by using proposed S-box I and proposed S-box II as shown in Figure 5. Histogram analyses is shown in Figure 6. Table 6 shows the comparison of proposed S-boxes with other S-boxes and the results obtained are good for encryption.

TABLE 6. MLC RESULT COMPARISON OF PROPOSED S-BOXES WITH DISTINGUISHED S-BOXES

Images	Entropy	Contrast	Correlation	Energy	Homogeneity
Plain image Pepper	7.5989	0.4618	0.9200	0.0999	0.8692
Plain image Baboon	7.4087	0.7727	0.7997	0.0779	0.7624
AES S-box [34]	7.9211	7.5509	0.0554	0.0202	0.4662
Gray S-box [26]	7.2301	7.5283	0.0586	0.0203	0.4623
Encrypted image Pepper by proposed S-box I round 1	7.5989	9.5525	0.1063	0.0180	0.4637
Encrypted image Pepper by proposed S-box II round 1	7.5989	8.7482	0.1135	0.0179	0.4662
Encrypted image Baboon proposed by S-box I round 1	7.4087	10.284	0.0121	0.0164	0.4041
Encrypted image Baboon proposed by S-box II round 1	7.4087	9.2989	0.0257	0.0168	0.4156

1(a)

1(b)

1(c)

1(d)

1(e)

1(f)

Figure 5. Visual representation of 1(a) Pepper's original image, 1(b) encrypted image of Pepper by S-box I, 1(c) encrypted image of Pepper by S-box II, 1(d) Baboon's original image, 1(e) encrypted image of Baboon by S-box I, 1(f) encrypted image of Baboon by S-box II.

Figure 6. Histogram analysis of 2(a) Pepper's original image, 2(b) encrypted image of Pepper by S-box I, 2(c) encrypted image of Pepper by S-box II, 2(d) Baboon's original image, 2(e) encrypted image of Baboon by S-box I, 2(f) encrypted image of Baboon by S-box II.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper presented a new method for constructing strong and resilient S-boxes based on binary tree built by variants of Depth First Search. We also evaluated the efficiency of our proposed S-boxes by using statistical analyses, algebraic analyses and noise removal scheme. We also compared our S-boxes with already existing S-boxes available in literature. The comparison depicts that our proposed S-boxes has the tendency to resist the cryptanalysis attack.

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